

NOTES

Equilibria of Transition Metal(II) Complexes of *p*-Acetylamino-phenyl-3,5-dinitro Salicylate Ion

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PHENETSAL (*p*-acetylamino-phenyl salicylate) has biological importance. The complexity constants of its dinitro derivative (*p*-acetylamino-phenyl-3,5-dinitro salicylate) Fe^{III} complexes were reported¹. The present paper deals with the determination of stepwise stability constants of complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *p*-acetylamino-phenyl-3,5-dinitro salicylate at 25 ± 1° with ionic strengths 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 *M* in alcohol water system 70 : 30 (v/v). Bjerrum-Calvin^{2,3} pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁴ has been used for the study. Thermodynamic stability constants at 25° are also reported.

Experimental

The metal salts of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade were used for the study. These were dissolved in double-distilled water to get 0.01 *M* solutions. The ligand, *p*-acetylamino-phenyl-3,5-dinitro salicylate, was prepared and purified by the method reported¹. Its 0.05 *M* solution was prepared in absolute alcohol. The required 0.05 *M* HClO₄ and 1.0 *M* NaClO₄ solutions were obtained in double-distilled water.

Systronics 322-1 pH meter having glass and calomel electrodes assembly, calibrated with buffer solutions, was used to measure pH during titration. SICO TBS thermostat was used to maintain constant temperature of titration mixture.

Results and Discussion

The ligand contains one OH group, and one proton is released during complexation. Due to the presence of carbonyl group the complexes may be chelates in nature. The titration curves were plotted between the volumes of the alkali added and B values (pH meter reading). The values of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and *pL* were calculated from the titration curves by Irving and Rossotti method⁵. The formation curves were plotted between $\bar{n}$ and *pL*. The value of $\bar{n}$ does not go beyond 2 and there is no sharp change in the formation curves. This suggests that 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes co-exist in solution. The

values of stability constants were calculated by half $\bar{n}$ method and linear extrapolation method⁶. The mean values are reported. The values of thermodynamic stability constants were calculated by plotting log *K_n* vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolating to zero ionic strength. The values of stability constants obtained in terms of log units are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL ION COMPLEXES OF *p*-ACETYLAMINOPHENYL-3,5-DINITRO SALICYLATE IN ALCOHOL-WATER SYSTEM 70 : 30 (v/v) AT 25°

Metal ion	Ionic strength <i>M</i>	Log <i>K₁</i>	Log <i>K₂</i>	Log β ₂
Mn ^{II}	0.00	4.45	3.74	8.19
	0.05	3.85	3.45	7.20
	0.10	3.82	3.32	7.15
	0.20	3.40	3.05	6.45
Co ^{II}	0.00	5.45	4.30	9.75
	0.05	4.85	3.90	8.75
	0.10	4.42	3.80	8.22
	0.20	4.12	3.58	7.80
Ni ^{II}	0.00	5.70	4.70	10.40
	0.05	5.45	4.22	9.67
	0.10	5.42	3.80	9.22
	0.20	5.30	3.60	8.90
Cu ^{II}	0.00	6.35	5.36	12.71
	0.05	5.75	4.82	10.57
	0.10	5.45	4.65	10.10
	0.20	5.22	4.30	9.52

The values of stabilities record a decrease with the rise of ionic strength. The order of stability of complexes is Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}. The stability order of complexes agrees with the order reported by Irving and Williams⁶.

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